

1 GETTING STARTED

1.1 Docker Image (Recommended)

Dockerhub (Recommended). Pull the `oopsla-artifact` tag from the dockerhub repository `erickoskinen/veracity`:

- `docker pull erickoskinen/veracity:oopsla-artifact`

Then run the docker image with `bash` (`docker run -it erickoskinen/veracity:oopsla-artifact bash`), change to the `veracity` directory, and compile with `make`.

Provided Image. Note the `veracity-artifact-docker.tar` file provided. Load the file with `docker` (`docker load -i veracity-artifact-docker.tar`), and run `bash` in the image. Finally, change to `veracity` directory, and compile with `make`.

1.2 Manual Build

With the files provided with this document, within the `veracity/src` directory, you will find all of the source and build scripts for Veracity.

Alternatively, if one wishes, one can pull from the Veracity Github¹.

Prerequisites.

- (1) Make sure OCaml, CMake, Opam, and Dune(>=2.9) are installed on the machine. We recommend an Arch based system, though we have also tested on Ubuntu.
- (2) Install `multicore-ocaml 4.12.0`².
This can be done with `opam update; opam switch create 4.12.0+domains+effects -repositories=multicore=git+https://github.com/ocaml-multicore/multicore-opam.git, default; opam switch 4.12.0+domains+effects; eval $(opam env)`
- (3) Install `cvc4`, either through the Linux package manager or the `cvc4 git`³.
- (4) Install `ppxlib.0.22.0` with effect syntax: `opam install ppxlib.0.22.0+effect-syntax`.
- (5) Install other dependencies: `opam install ppx_deriving_yaml ounit2 ctypes-foreign sexplib`.
- (6) Optional dependencies: install `cvc5` and `z3`.

Finally, build Veracity from the `veracity` directory with `make`.

Running Veracity. Veracity requires dynamic linking for a library built during the process. Thus it requires `.` in the `ld` library path. The shell script `vcy.sh` is provided to automate that part.

A Veracity source file can be run like so:

```
./vcy.sh interp <vcy file> [command line parameters].
```

Example: `./vcy.sh interp ../benchmarks/manual/dihedral.vcy 10 5 0 2 1`

For running trials shown in Fig2, execute as follows:

- Group1 (Inferring commutativity conditions):
`./vcy.sh infer ../benchmarks/{inferred|inferred_loops}/{BenchmarkName}.vcy`
Example: `./vcy.sh infer ../benchmarks/inferred/counter.vcy`
- Group2 (Verifying commutativity conditions): commute condition should be provided in the code as `commute(cond)`.
`./vcy.sh verify ../benchmarks/verify/{BenchmarkName}.vcy`
Example: `./vcy.sh verify ../benchmarks/verify/array1.vcy`

¹<https://github.com/veracity-lang/veracity/commit/9cfe9c2ac39305be0a838acb6f028ae78281d399>

The commit linked is similar to the artifact but includes some additional files and fixes a few inconsistent names.

²<https://github.com/ocaml-multicore/ocaml-multicore>

³<https://cvc4.github.io/downloads.html>

If the other solvers are installed, those can be used by adding `-prover <cvc5|z3>` to an `interp` command.

2 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

Once Veracity is built as per the instructions in Section 1, the only script that needs to be run is `./reports/bench_all.sh`. The script should be run in the `reports` directory. This script requires Python 3 to be installed. As before with the `ld` library path, it assumes an Arch environment, or at least one where `LD_LIBRARY_PATH=xxx` works.

The script should take several hours (3-5 on a relatively high-end machine. Definitely much longer on a laptop). To remove some of the computationally heavy trials, some of the input sizes on line 38-39 of `speedup_gen.py` may be commented out.

Explanation of files output.

- `inference_table.tex`: A table of abridged conditions inferred and the time it took.
- `inference_table_unabridged.tex`: The same but without trimming long conditions inferred.
- `verify_table.tex`: A table of results for condition verification with time taken for verification.
- `test/ratio.csv`: csv table showing speedup ratio for the main tests, geomean across 4 trials. Each trial is `ratioN.csv`, and the raw times are available as `parN.csv` and `seqN.csv`.
- `test/crowdfund/ratio.csv`: Same, but just for the crowdfund case study.
- `test/filesystem/ratio.csv`: Same, but just for the filesystem case study.

To recreate the graphs in the paper, merely plot speedup ratio against log size by benchmark in any spreadsheet software, such as Excel.

3 RELEVANCE TO PAPER

Claims Supported by the Artifact. :

- We can achieve speedup for large enough problem sizes by conditionally executing in parallel.
- Locking technique has small overhead.
- Inference is generally fast & creates useful conditions.
- Verification is even faster, and can work for cases where inference does not.

Claims Not Supported by the Artifact:

- Locking technique can be done automatically.